

Title:

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECT OF SELF-MEDICATION AMONG PROFESSIONAL HEALTH WORKERS IN ABUJA

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Ethical Approval:

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aims to assess the prevalence, types, and motivations for self-medication among healthcare professionals in Abuja, Nigeria.

Design: A cross-sectional survey.

Setting: Selected hospitals in Abuja, Nigeria.

Participants: 348 healthcare professionals, including doctors, nurses, and pharmacists, who provided informed consent, participated in the study.

Intervention: No specific interventions were implemented in this study. However, the study underscores the need for educational programs to address the risks of self-medication among healthcare professionals in Abuja.

Primary and Secondary Outcome Measures: The study examines self-medication prevalence, types of medications used, motivations for self-medication, and its impact on professional performance and healthcare quality.

Results: The findings reveal that 59.8% of participants reported rarely self-medicating, while 23.6% self-medicated weekly, 14.7% monthly, and only 1.7% did so daily. The study indicates moderate levels of self-medication among healthcare professionals, raising concerns about its implications for healthcare quality.

Conclusions: The study underscores the necessity for targeted interventions to enhance adherence to guidelines and promote safer healthcare practices in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Nigeria.

Keywords:

Self Medication; Health Personnel; Drug Misuse; Pharmaceutical Preparations; Nigeria

Strengths and Limitations of this study:

This study's strengths include a diverse sample of healthcare professionals and a robust design. However, limitations include reliance on self-reported data, which may introduce bias, and a cross-sectional design, which limits causal inferences.

INTRODUCTION

Self-medication, the practice of treating one's health issues without professional consultation, is prevalent globally, particularly among healthcare professionals who should ideally adhere to higher standards of medical practice. This behavior poses significant health risks, including incorrect self-diagnosis, drug interactions, and potential drug dependence and resistance.

Healthcare professionals, due to their medical knowledge and access to medications, may be more prone to self-medication compared to the general population. In Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory (FCT), the healthcare system grapples with limited resources, high patient loads, and inadequate healthcare infrastructure. These challenges may drive healthcare professionals to self-medicate as a coping mechanism to manage stress, save time, or avoid the inconvenience of formal medical consultations. Weak regulatory controls and low compliance with existing regulations further exacerbate the issue, leading to the misuse of medications and associated risks like incorrect diagnoses and antibiotic resistance. Ethical concerns also arise, questioning the responsible use of medical knowledge and resources.

This study aims to explore the prevalence and implications of self-medication among healthcare professionals in the FCT, shedding light on its extent, underlying reasons, and potential impact on their performance and healthcare delivery. By examining these practices, the study seeks to identify the unique factors influencing self-medication behaviors in Nigerian hospitals and provide recommendations for mitigating these practices. Ultimately, the goal is to offer insights for targeted interventions to improve regulatory controls, enhance compliance, and promote safer medication practices, thereby improving the health and performance of healthcare providers and the quality of patient care.

The primary objectives of this study are:

- I. To determine the prevalence of self-medication among healthcare professionals in selected hospitals in the FCT.
- II. To identify the types of medications commonly used for self-medication.
- III. To explore the motivations behind self-medication practices.
- IV. To evaluate the impact of self-medication on professional performance and healthcare quality.
- V. To provide recommendations for interventions to mitigate self-medication practices.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous studies, such as Adzic Lukovic et al. (2014) and Ali *et al.* (2012), have highlighted the risks associated with self-medication, including the potential for misuse and adverse health outcomes. This study draws from the Theory of Planned Behavior and Social Cognitive Theory.

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB): Ajzen (1991) suggests that an individual's intention to engage in a behavior is influenced by their attitude towards the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. In self-medication, healthcare professionals' attitudes towards self-medication, the influence of peer practices, and their confidence in managing their health contribute to their behaviors.

Social Cognitive Theory (SCT): Bandura's theory emphasizes observational learning, imitation, and modeling in behavior acquisition. Healthcare professionals may engage in self-medication after observing peers or mentors doing the same, influenced by perceived benefits and lack of immediate negative consequences. SCT also highlights the role of self-efficacy and outcome expectations, where professionals believe they can effectively manage their health through self-medication.

Methodology

This study was conducted in Abuja, the capital city of Nigeria, from January to May 2024. Abuja, centrally located in Nigeria, spans about 1,476 km² with an estimated population of around 2,238,800 in 2015. The research focused on the issue of self-medication among healthcare professionals, highlighting how these individuals, who typically provide medical advice, often diagnose and treat their own health problems without consulting their peers. This practice can lead to incorrect diagnoses, delays in seeking proper care, and misuse of medications.

Abuja's diverse cultural and professional landscape made it an ideal location for this study. With a mix of public (26.6%) and private (73.4%) health facilities among the 906 total health facilities in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), the city offered a unique environment to examine self-medication practices among healthcare workers from various backgrounds.

Study Population

The study involved 348 healthcare professionals, including doctors, nurses, pharmacists, and other allied healthcare workers in the FCT.

Study Design

A cross-sectional study design was used to assess the prevalence and impact of self-medication among healthcare professionals at a specific point in time.

Sampling Technique

A stratified random sampling technique ensured representation from various categories of healthcare facilities (public hospitals, private clinics, and pharmacies), with participants randomly selected within each stratum.

Data Collection

Data were gathered through structured questionnaires covering demographic information, self-medication practices, reasons for self-medication, types of ailments treated, sources of information, and the perceived impact on health.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics provided an overview of the study population and the prevalence of self-medication. Measures such as mean, median, standard deviation, and frequency distributions were calculated and presented through tables, graphs, and summary statistics.

The mean ($\bar{x}$) Was calculated as:

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\sum xi}{n}$$

Where $\sum xi$ is the sum of all observations and N is the number of observations.

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (x_i - \mu)^2}{N}}$$

The standard deviation (σ) was calculated using the formula:

where (x_i) represents each observation and ($\bar{x}$) is the mean of the observations. and N is the number of observations.

The prevalence of self-medication was summarized using percentages, and the types of ailments and medications used were presented as frequency distributions.

RESULTS

The results indicate a moderate prevalence of self-medication among healthcare professionals in the FCT. Table 1 shows the frequency of self-medication. Table 2 outlines the types of medications commonly self-prescribed. Motivations for self-medication, as shown in Table 3, include convenience, time constraints, and confidence in personal medical knowledge.

Table 1: Frequency of Self-Medication

This table details how often respondents engage in self-medication.

Frequency	Count	Percent	Description
Daily	6	1.7%	Respondents who self-medicate on a daily basis.
Weekly	82	23.6%	Respondents who self-medicate at least once a week.
Monthly	51	14.7%	Respondents who self-medicate approximately once a month.
Rarely	208	59.8%	Respondents who self-medicate only on rare occasions.
Never	1	0.3%	Respondents who never engage in self-medication.
Total	348	100%	Represents the total number of respondents surveyed.

Table 2: Types of Medications Commonly Self-Prescribed

This table outlines the categories of medications respondents typically choose when self-medication.

Medication Type	Count	Percent	Description
Over the Counter (OTC) Drugs	217	62.4%	Respondents primarily using medications available without a prescription.
Prescription Drugs	8	2.3%	Respondents self-medication with prescription-only drugs.
Others (e.g., herbal remedies)	80	23.0%	Respondents using alternative remedies or medications outside standard categories.
More than one option	43	12.4%	Respondents who indicated using multiple types of medications.
Total	348	100%	Represents the total number of respondents surveyed.

Table 3: Motivations for Self-Medication

This table lists the reasons why healthcare professionals choose to self-medicate.

Commonly Self-Prescribed Medications	Count	Percent	Description
Over-the-counter pain relievers	46	13.2%	Medications like ibuprofen, aspirin, acetaminophen commonly used for pain management.
Antihistamines for allergies	6	1.7%	Medications used to relieve allergy symptoms.
Cough and cold medications	5	1.4%	Medications for relieving cough, cold, or flu symptoms.
Antacids or digestive aids	1	0.3%	Medications to treat heartburn or indigestion.

DISCUSSION

The results reveal significant insights into self-medication among healthcare professionals in Abuja, highlighting both the prevalence of self-medication practices and the motivations behind these behaviors. The high percentage of respondents self-medicating reflects a concerning trend that could have broader implications for patient care quality.

The predominant motivations—convenience, time constraints, and confidence in personal medical knowledge—suggest a need for further education and awareness regarding the risks associated with self-medication. While healthcare professionals may possess medical knowledge, the risks of misdiagnosis and inappropriate treatment remain significant.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that self-medication is a prevalent practice among healthcare professionals in Abuja, influenced by various factors including convenience, time constraints, and confidence in self-treatment. To improve healthcare quality, it is imperative to address these motivations through targeted interventions, emphasizing the importance of consulting with peers and adhering to medical guidelines.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no financial, personal, or professional conflicts of interest related to this research.

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AUTHOR STATEMENT

Shamsiya Ibrahim: Led the study design, methodology development, and data collection process; drafted the manuscript and critically reviewed its content; provided final approval of the version to be published; and is accountable for all aspects of the work.

Ibrahim Sabo Adamu: Contributed to the study design and methodology; assisted in data collection; reviewed the manuscript critically; and approved the final version for publication, ensuring the integrity of the data.

Professor Amos Nworie: Provided supervisory oversight of the research project; reviewed and contributed to the manuscript's intellectual content; approved the final version for publication; and ensured adherence to ethical standards.

DATA ACCESS STATEMENT

The data supporting this study are available at [insert data repository link here] with the DOI [insert DOI here].

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